

STUDY MATERIAL OF NEUROLINGUISTICS, NEUROLINGUISTIC PROGRAMMING TECHNIQUE, APHASIA

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Abstract: Neurolinguistics comes from the words "neuron" and "linguistics". harvest has been word being, then a person in the brain of cells speech harvest to do processes learns. It actively serves in the creation of language and speech units, it is the leader. Accordingly, neurolinguistics sheds light on the organic, constant, necessary relationship between the human nervous system and the communication tool - language.

Key words : Key words : neuron , NLP , neurolinguistic programming , analyzers ,

This science examines the question of whether speech activity is a product of the brain, the impact of brain disease on speech activity. Simply put, one of the objects of study of neurolinguistics is aphasia, and the other is neurolinguistic programming (NLP).

The issue of damage to the speech zone of the brain and, as a result, impaired speech activity, was mentioned in the works of our grandfathers Ibn Sina and Beruni, and although they paid attention to the treatment of this disease, it could not be formed as a separate branch of science.¹

Neuropsychology and related neurolinguistics were formed as a special science only recently - in the seventies of the last century. The creation of this science was greatly contributed by such scientists as NA Eisler, AA Leontev, AR Luria, ES Bain, RM Boskis, EN Venarskaya.

In the field of neurolinguistics, neurolinguistic schools have appeared even in Russia, which have played a leading role in the development of the field.

Speech information process, that is, the process of people giving information to each other and receiving information from each other with the help of mutual speech, is considered the object of study of several sciences. In particular, this process is defined by the sciences of linguistics and psychology. Linguistics separates the language, which is the main means of communication of people, and the speech that occurs in the process of direct communication and interaction, internal structure, structural units, the various occurrences of these structural units in the speech process, "internal structure" studied a number of issues, such as the main stages of the transition from "external structure" to "external structure" and the mutual relations of the above two structures.

Man reflects existence in his mind. Reflection is carried out with the help of sense organs. Sensory organs transmit certain information about the external world to the brain. The brain summarizes this information. It seems that the process of reflecting the objective world comes to the surface through the central nervous system, the brain.

The nervous system generally includes two groups of nervous systems:

¹ A.Primov " of Linguistics current problems " page 52 Urganch 2019

1) central nervous system and 2) peripheral nervous system. Informative speech about existence and its understanding is carried out by the direction of the border nervous system towards the center. Peripheral nervous systems provide the central nervous system with information about certain signs of objects and events that are objectively present. That is why the organs related to the borderline nervous system are called analyzers (analyzers). They are organs of sight, hearing, and taste. Two types of nerve structures are distinguished in each analyzer.

- 1) the structure that conveys information from this sensory organ to the brain membrane;
- 2) the structure that guides the objects of existence (cognitive zone of the brain).

As the third level, the zone of the lingual membrane with a complex anatomical structure is distinguished. In this zone, the complex of symbols from different analyzers of the brain is combined, and as a result, it is possible to move from sensory perception to language generalization.

Speech formation, language behavior is revealed through the opposite movement: movement from the center to the border. The speech program formed in the zone covered by the brain analyzers is concretized in the zone of speech practice and comes to the surface with the help of the projection movement system with the participation of the speech organs (as well as the system that produces written speech).

In contrast to the praxial system of the brain (sensory or motor), the gnosticpraxic veil and veil analyzer zone are characterized by functional asymmetry: the language system and thought expressed through speech are connected with its hemisphere.

The human brain is a complex functional system that continuously operates with the participation of at least three main blocks. One of them ensures the triggering of the curtain and gives the possibility of a long implementation of the form of selective activity. Another provides information acquisition, processing and storage. The third is responsible for programming, management and control of activities.

Damage to the above-mentioned blocks has a negative effect on their normal function. Damage to the apparatus belonging to the first block limits the ability to select and select mental activity. Damage to the second unit's hardware causes the loss of the ability to receive, process and store information. Damage to the third unit limits the possibility of programming, stable management and control.

It seems that any damage to the brain has a negative effect on a certain part of human activity. As a result, the ability to accept oral and written speech decreases. In the case of speech agnosia, the patient forgets the sound "appearance" of the native language (speech-auditory agnosia) or the appearance of letters in written speech "speech-vision agnosia", while maintaining good vision and hearing. At this time, the patient can speak or write. A patient with auditory-speech agnosia can read, and a patient with visual-speech agnosia can explain his or her speech.

When speech apraxia occurs, the opposite situation is encountered. At this time, the patient's speech and writing movements are disturbed, he cannot pronounce and write sounds and words. But the ability to understand the speech of people around and read their writings can be preserved.

When the membrane zone of the analyzers is damaged, the condition of aphasia increases. At this time, any speech activity: hearing, seeing, pronouncing, reading also fades. If the source of damage is moderate, the patient's ability to distinguish sounds in words is lost. It confuses

words that are phonetically close. Sometimes in the case of aphasia, he can mechanically repeat what he hears or reads without understanding the meaning.

For neurolinguistics, the brain damage of bilingual and multilingual people (polyglots) provides a lot of material. At this time, the patient can completely forget the second language or mix elements of several languages while preserving one language to a certain extent.

Neurolinguistics, by identifying the above conditions, creates a great opportunity for effective treatment of patients. Recent advances in linguistics and medicine continue to improve neurolinguistics testing methods. Nowadays, neurolinguistics is blessed with the ideas and methods of intermediate sciences such as psycholinguistics, neuropsychology, neurophysiology, psychoacoustics, cybernetics. Thus, neurolinguistics is developing as a branch of comprehensive study of the nature of human definition of the world.

If we translate neuro-linguistic programming into our language, the words "nerve language" and "programming" are derived. Or, to put it in plain language, it means programming a person with the help of language and words. Today, hypnotists and manipulators are using neuro-linguistic programming to achieve their goals.

Below are some techniques of neuro-linguistic programming.

This technique can be called the basis of NLD. Because with its help, you have the opportunity to influence a person as you wish, and you can control his behavior. This technique is also the basis of hypnosis. In order to manage another person, it is necessary to adapt to him first. To adapt, you need to get into the rhythm of your interlocutor's movements. It can be his posture, gaze, holding the body, the position of his hands, the position of his legs, the rhythm of breathing, etc. But the most important thing is to get into his mood. Adapting to the rhythm of breathing gives great results.

You observe your interlocutor's breathing and remain silent when he breathes in, and speak when he breathes out. As a result, his subconscious will have the impression that your words are being spoken by him. Let's say that your interlocutor is getting angry and is puffing up like a deflated balloon. Your goal is to make him angry. In this case, you will also speed up your psyche and enter the same physiological state as when you are angry. This will be your adaptation to the interlocutor. In this case, you will continue the conversation with him and during the conversation, you will gradually brake your psyche.

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